

REACTANCE OF BLOOD CIRCULATION SYSTEM AT PERSONS WITH NORMOTENSIVE TYPE OF REACTION TO PHYSICAL LOADING

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Introduction. In modern practice medico-pedagogical monitoring of persons engaged in physical and sports activities, essential place occupied by functional diagnostic methods, involving the establishment the level of the functional state of the organism and its adaptive capabilities, as well as identifying early signs of prepathological and pathological conditions associated with the influence of physical training and sports [1,3]. An important role is given to conducting tests with measured physical load, allowing to identify tolerance to the effect of load.

Methodology. The purpose of this study was the reaction of the circulatory system for spontaneous breath in patients with normotensive type of reaction to dosed physical load. We used a modern method of spiroarteriocardiography (SACR). Note that SACR is a complex multifunctional methodology study of the cardiorespiratory system, which allows the simultaneous recording mode to determine the level of cardiac pump function, autonomic regulation of HR, systolic and diastolic blood pressure and spontaneous breathing [2,4]. However, the greatest attentions, in our opinion, deserve options SACR characterizing variability of HR and BP at different phases of the respiratory cycle (Fig. 8).

Fig.8. A typical image of intersystem relations cardiovascular and respiratory systems in various phases of spontaneous respiration.

Given the nature of changes in HR and BP during spontaneous breathing (Fig. 8), when the length changes of the cardiac cycle and blood pressure did not fit into the duration of the cycle of breathing, it is advisable to take into account the parameters listed below.

The physiological significance of these parameters was discussed earlier and can be interpreted as follows [4]:

1) the level was originally registered an absolute decline in SBP (SBPmin) - most likely determines the amount of the deposit of blood in the lung tissue during inspiration;

2) time of absolute decline in BP (TBPmin) - most likely determines the rate of incorporation of extracardiac mechanisms of compensation for inspiration;

3) the level was originally registered the maximum absolute increase in heart rate (HRmax) - likely to determine the degree of compensation of peripheral circulation as inspiration;

4) the time to the absolute increase in heart rate (THRmax) - most likely determines the rate of incorporation of mechanisms to maintain the tone of peripheral vessels;

5) the rate of absolute BP reduction (BPmin / TBPmin) - most likely, is an integral indicator implementation baroreflex and mechanical influences on the maintenance of BP;

6) the rate of absolute increase in heart rate (HRmax / THRmax) - most likely, is an integral indicator of peripheral vascular resistance;

7) the difference of time absolute changes of blood pressure and heart rate (THRmax – TBPmin) - most likely characterizes the dominant mechanism for the maintenance of BP.

Based on these assumptions, we have previously [4] was carried ranking marked the parameters in the healthy population in accordance with the percentile distribution (Tab 14.).

Table 14.

Percentile distribution indices of SACR in virtually healthy population

	< 5	5-25	25-75	75-95	>95
TBPmin, s	< 0,9	0,9 – 1,0	1,1 - 1,4	1,5 - 1,8	> 1,8
BPmin, mmHg	< -8,2	-8,2 - -5,11	-5,12 - -2,45	-2,46 - -1,14	> -1,14
THRmax, s	< 1,1	1,1 - 1,3	1,3 - 2	2 - 2,6	> 2,6
HRmax, 1/min	< 0,94	0,94 - 2,5	2,5 - 8,18	8,18 - 14,9	> 14,9
HRmax/ THRmax, 1/min/s	< 0,6	0,6 - 1,56	1,56 - 4,8	4,8 - 9,08	> 9,08
BPmin/ TBPmin mmHg/s	< -6,45	-6,45 - -4,11	-4,11 - -2,06	-2,06 - -1,13	> -1,13
THRmax - TBPmin	< -0,1	-0,1 - 0,2	0,2 - 0,7	0,7 - 1,3	> 1,3

Results.

To solve this problem, we examined 226 male and female aged 18 to 25, who along with SACR-sample survey was conducted test of Martinet-Kushelevsky, which was estimated by methods of Letunov and Klochkov and allowed to determine the type of reaction to dosed physical load. In accordance with the findings of normotensive different type of reaction was observed in 107

individuals, and good in 60 normotensive individuals, which are further and formed two study groups, which results were compared with population distribution, the corresponding percentile range 0-5%, 5-25%; 25-75%, 75-95% and 95-100% of occurrence.

Fig. 9. Distribution of indicators TBPmin (a) and BPmin, mmHg (b) in the group with normotensive excellent and normotensive good response to physical load.

Analyzing the data distribution parameters of the absolute risk reduction and time reduction of blood pressure during inspiration, it should be noted that the mode of occurrence rate TBPmin shifted into a zone of moderate increase (Fig. 9a), and normotensive with a good response to 3 times more often expected (60.9% vs. 20%), while normotensive than in 2,3 times (46,7% vs. 20%). Under this option, a significant increase in time BP decrease during inspiration in both cases, occurred in 2.5 times more expected (13.3% and 13%, respectively, compared with 5% expected). At the same time reducing the time BP reduction with good and excellent reaction is extremely rare in 4,4% of cases in the first and 1,3% of cases in the second. Coordinates these with absolute values of BP reduction during inspiration (Fig. 9b), a fashion which although it is within normal limits, but the options for a moderate decline in excellent response higher than expected at 1.6 times (32% vs. 20%), and the options expressed by decline in favorable reaction in 1,7 times (8,7% vs 5%). It should also be noted that a slight decrease in blood pressure during inspiration with excellent type is quite rare (12% vs. 20% and 1.3% vs 5%), while in good - practically corresponds to the expected (19.6% vs. 20% and 4.3 to 5%).

That is, in normotensive type of response to dosed physical stress during the growth of arterial pressure during inspiration is significantly greater than in the population, despite the fact that the absolute reduction in BP virtually the norm with a certain tendency towards a moderate increase in the excellent and marked increase in the normotensive good reaction.

Analyzing the values of time increase in heart rate and absolute increase in heart rate (Fig. 10, b) it should be noted that the mode of occurrence rate THRmax corresponds to a population, but there is enough clear upward trend, as in good or excellent response to the type of physical activity with a very rare occurrence options to reduce the time of growth - at 1.2% with excellent and 4.4% with good type of reaction to physical load. Moreover, the distribution was not significantly

different from each other (Fig. 10 a). At the same time in terms of HRmax notes some differences associated with a greater predominance of options to increase the absolute values of heart rate during inspiration with excellent type of response. At the same time in both types of responses frequently found variants of a significant increase in heart rate during inspiration: for good - in 2,5 times, in very good - 2 times greater than expected (Fig. 10 b). Moderate and marked reduction in HR increase at the inspiration phase is uncommon for both types and amount, respectively, found in 6,5% and 6,1% of cases.

a **b**
Fig. 10. Distribution of indicators THRmax (a) and HRmax (b) in the group with normotensive excellent and normotensive good response to physical load.

Significantly complements the above information analysis of the indicators the rate of increase in heart rate and rate of BP decrease during inspiration (Fig. 11 a, b). Indicator HRmax / THRmax characterized by an extremely well-balanced settings with some tendency to a moderate increase, with more pronounced with excellent type of response to physical load, which allows to confirm the previously noted data on good lability of the vascular wall, providing vascular resistance at each cardiac cycle (Fig. 11a).

a **b**
Fig. 11. Distribution of indicators HRmax/THRmax (a) and BPmin/TBpmin (b) in the group with normotensive excellent and normotensive good response to physical load.

Immediately, we note that small variations in heart rate response to breath marked with excellent type only 9,8% of cases, more than 2,5 times less expected, while in the good in 17,3% cases - 1,5 times less expected. On the other hand the rate of reduction of blood pressure during inspiration, is characterized by the redistribution towards higher values, ie absolute values of BP reduction lower (Fig. 11b). Moreover, if other than the type of response to physical exercise stress is concentrated at the level of prevalence of moderate decrease of 38,7% against 20%

of the expected level in a pronounced decrease of 12,0% to 5% of the expected, then the good type of stress reaction at the level of dominance observed significant decrease 17,4% to 5% of the expected (3 times more often). That is, the rate of increase in heart rate and rate of BP decline with excellent and good response to the types of physical activity is significantly higher than in the population. The rate of decline of blood pressure was more pronounced than the rate of increase in heart rate, which can qualitatively characterize normotensive type response during the test with an adjustable one-time six minute breathing. At the same time, marked reduction of rates of change in heart rate and blood pressure during inspiration was not found in the excellent style and very little in the good.

Fig. 12. Distribution of indicators $THR_{max} - TBP_{min}$ in the group with normotensive excellent and normotensive good response to physical load.

Supplements previous data information on the distribution of such derived measures as the difference between the time of growth in HR and BP, which characterizes the predominant mechanism for maintaining BP when the decline in the predominance of the rate of incorporation of the vascular component, and its rate of increase in the prevalence of cardiac, when the rate of increase in heart rate still prevails above the rate of BP increase. It is interesting that other than the type of response to physical stress distribution indices ($THR_{max} - TBP_{min}$) almost completely corresponds to the expected, while in good – a modest shift towards the predominance of the vascular component in the maintenance of BP (Fig. 12).

Discussion. The redistribution of contributions by the time and the absolute values of increase in heart rate, more pronounced with excellent normotensive type of reaction, characterized by a higher compensatory capacity of peripheral circulation. A typical differential feature normotensive type of reaction is the lack of hit rate of negative growth rate of BP in the range of 2 (95 - 100%) and a significant reduction in hits this indicator in a range (75 - 95%), with significant predominance of deposits in the range of -2 (0 - 5%) and -1 (5 - 25%). To differentiate excellent and good normotensive type reaction indicative differences in terms of velocity increment in heart rate, which is in excellent form never falls into the range - 2 (0 - 5%) and lack of hits in margin growth time ($THR_{max} - TBP_{min}$) in good form in the range 2 (95 - 100%). The distribution of the indicator with excellent normotensive type of reaction is fully consistent with a population that characterizes the synchronization mechanisms for the maintenance of systemic hemodynamics, which is a good option for some desinchron due to the predominance of the vascular component of the regulation.

Conclusions. Thus, the results of studies using of SACR, as well as their analysis of patients with normotensive type of reaction to physical stress has revealed the characteristic features of heart rate and blood pressure response in the respiratory cycle, suggesting the differentiation of this type with massive studies of healthy persons and persons with disabilities. In addition, the specific features of excellent and good options normotensive response that will be useful for express surveys of persons engaged in different sports.

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